

GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN UNIVERSITIES AND RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS

NATIONAL FIELDWORK REPORT

Country: Bulgaria

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1. INTRODUCTION

The current research could not identify any information about gender-based violence in universities and research organisations in Bulgaria. Due to this, the attitudes towards GBV in academia in the country, as well as their evolution over the last five years, are a complex issue.

As a whole, there is a lack of understanding of the term 'gender-based violence' in Bulgarian society. Gender equality issues are often seen as secondary and unimportant since it's perceived that policy-makers have more significant and pressing topics to focus their attention on and to direct the state funding too. GBV is only starting to appear in the public discourse due to the efforts of NGOs and in relation to European Union legislation and projects. It is thus safe to say that in the public sphere, GBV is not very known or is often understood as domestic violence or mixed up with it.

As for the field of higher education and research in Bulgaria in general, regrettably, it has been in stagnation for decades now. The structures are rigid and do not provide many opportunities for evolving and modernisation. Many of the key positions in the field, such as leading positions in the research departments of universities and decision-making councils at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, are taken up by elderly members of the scientific community, often men. They are not very open to change or adhere to more conservative values. There is also no political will to shake up the academic arena either through laws and policies.

2. MAPPING OF POLICIES AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

The present research could not identify any laws, policies, and strategies at the national or regional level or at the level of RFOs that address GBV in universities and research organisations. More specifically, none of the following elements of the 7P model was found:

- Prevalence and incidence data - no information about the scale of the problem
- Prevention measures such as awareness-raising initiatives, educational materials, or training of professionals
- Protection actions to safeguard potential victims and report occurrences
- Prosecution and disciplinary measures specifically targeting GBV
- Provision of services to victims, families, and perpetrators of GBV

- Partnerships between relevant actors such as governmental agencies, civil society organisations, trade unions, staff or student associations
- Policies targeted at GBV

While there are no laws specifically targeting GBV in universities and research organisations, certain other laws can be used to address GBV in the context of the labour market:

- The Law on Equality between Women and Men (2016) - mentions that it's based on the principles of "not allowing discrimination and gender-based violence."
- The Law on Protection Against Discrimination (2004) - guarantees the equal treatment of all individuals.
 - Article 5 stipulates that sexual harassment, among other actions, shall be deemed discrimination.
 - Article 17 states that an employer who has received a complaint from an employee, considering him/herself a victim of harassment, including sexual harassment, at the workplace must immediately carry out an investigation, take measures to stop the harassment, as well as impose a disciplinary sanction in case the harassment has been committed by another worker or employee.
 - Additional Provision 1 (2) states that "sexual harassment" is "any unwanted conduct of sexual character expressed physically, verbally or in any other manner, which violates the dignity or honour or creates hostile, degrading, humiliating or intimidating environment and, in particular when the refusal to accept such conduct or the compulsion thereto could influence the taking of decisions, affecting the person."
- Criminal Code (1968, last changes in 2021)
 - Special Part, Chapter II, Section II Bodily Injury - Article 128 states that a person who has caused a severe bodily injury leading to continuous disturbance of consciousness; permanent blindness of one or both eyes; permanent deafness; loss of speech, reproduction inability; disfigurement which causes permanent disturbance of the speech or of a sensory organ; loss of one kidney, the spleen or a lung lobe; loss or mutilation of a leg or an arm; permanent general health impairment, dangerous to life is punished by deprivation of liberty for three to ten years. Article 129 states that a person who has caused a medium bodily injury leading to permanent weakening of the eyesight or hearing; permanent disturbance of speech, difficulties of the movement of the extremities, the body or the neck, disturbance of the functions of the genital organs without causing reproductive incapacity; breaking of a jaw or knocking out of teeth, without which chewing or speech are impaired; disfigurement of the face or of other parts of the body; permanent impairment of health not dangerous to life or impairment of health temporarily dangerous to life; injuries which penetrate into the cranial, thoracic and abdominal cavities, is punished by deprivation of liberty for up to five years. Article 130 (last amended in 1993) states that a person who has caused a trivial bodily injury causing pain or suffering without

- impairment of health is punished by deprivation of liberty for up to six months or probation or a fine from BGN one hundred to three hundred.
 - Special Part, Chapter II, Section V Coercion - Article 143 (last amended in 1997) states that a person who compels another to do, to omit or to suffer something contrary to his will, using for that purpose force, threats or abuse of his authority, shall be punished by deprivation of liberty for up to six years.
 - General Part, Chapter IV, Section II Kinds of Punishment, Articles 42a-42b on probation measures - Article 42a states that probation measures include compulsory registration at the current address, mandatory regular appointments with a probation officer and restrictions on free movement, among others. Article 42b states that the probation measure of restrictions on free movement can consist of prohibition to attending locations, areas, and establishments, as strictly specified in the sentence.
- Criminal Procedure Code (2006, last changes in 2021)
 - Article 67 'Prohibition to Approach the Victim' - Article 67 'Prohibition to Approach the Victim' states that at the proposal of the prosecutor with the consent of the victim or at the request of the victim, the competent first-instance court may prohibit the accused party from directly approaching the victim.

The main actors in Bulgaria that would be involved in creating GBV-targeting laws, policies and strategies for the higher education and research sector include the Ministry of Education and Science, which is in charge of the field of higher education and research organisations; the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy (Equal Opportunities, Anti-discrimination and Social Assistance Benefits (EOADSAB) Department, a part of the Ministry's Policy on Disability, Equal Opportunities and Social Assistance Benefits Directorate), which is the charge of gender equality issues; and the National Council for Gender Equality with Bulgaria's Ministerial Council, which is a platform for collaboration between policy-makers and civil society on the issues of gender equality in the country. The Ministry of Economy is in charge of the innovation policy of the country, which thus may have a say in research funding. Members of Parliament and the Parliamentary Committee on Education, Science, Children, Youths and Sports Committee can formulate laws and make changes to the National Strategy for Scientific Research. In the email exchange related to the current research, the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy noted that any specific measures on GBV in the field of higher education and research would be the responsibility of the respective institution, in this case - the Ministry of Education and Science.

In addition, the main RFO in the country is the National Science Fund, which is a part of the Ministry of Education and Science. In the email exchange with the Director of the Fund, Prof Georgi Vayssilov, in relation to the present research, his answer was that it is not in his competency to address the issue (GBV).

The main research organisation is the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. The National Assembly of the Republic of Bulgaria allocates the budget for research and makes decisions for the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, and the Academy reports to it.

In the context of how the topic of GBV is treated in Bulgaria, it is difficult to assess the extent to which the national, regional, and RFO policies have an impact on the organisational level of HEIs and RPOs. The topic is not brought into the spotlight at all, so there are no such policies for the time being - which can be assessed as to how they impact HEIs and RPOs.

The present research could not identify any other relevant activities to combat GBV in universities and research organisations at the national or regional level or in RFOs.

RPOs in Bulgaria, with the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences being the main one in addition to some universities, are not a steady source of knowledge on GBV. Instead, it is usually NGOs dealing with gender topics that address GBV in different contexts. The present research could not identify the topic of GBV in curricula and in teaching in universities. When gender topics are present in certain research papers, they are usually the result of the personal interest of specific researchers.

3. DEBATES REGARDING #METOO AND THE ISTANBUL CONVENTION

The international #MeToo movement did not result in a significant change in the public opinion in Bulgaria towards issues of sexual violence and GBV. When the scandals erupted in the U.S. and Europe, they were covered in Bulgarian news, but in the context of curious international events rather than a tangible topic that applies to the country. Later on, some NGOs and individuals picked up the discourse, trying to raise attention towards the issues in Bulgaria. However, soon enough, the debates were suffocated by 'anti-gender' rhetorics. It does not appear that the #MeToo movement debates thus had a significant impact on universities and research organisations in Bulgaria.

The debates around the #MeToo movement in Bulgaria coincided with the unsuccessful attempt for ratification of the Istanbul Convention in 2018. The ruling party at the time, GERB, attempted to introduce the Convention and push it for ratification as a sign of goodwill to the country's European partners. However, there was strong pushback from many of the political parties. The Council of Europe document was thus not ratified after lengthy political, social, and even religious debates. The Convention was even declared by the Constitutional Court to be in contradiction with the Bulgarian constitution. The Bulgarian Orthodox Church also took a position against the Istanbul Convention because, according to it, it contradicted the natural order in the world. A number of family-oriented NGOs appeared in the public arena, some created very recently, which took a hard stance against the Convention. The well-known gender equality-focused NGOs remained the only real proponents of the Convention, but with no success. In fact, it later became (unofficially) known that one of the NGOs whose name contains the word 'gender' was asked to change its name in order to receive state funding for its activities.

The reasons for this unfortunate turn of events with the Istanbul Convention in Bulgaria are multifaceted. On the surface, the hot issue was the term 'gender,' which was taken out of context. With rigorous media coverage and online propaganda, both political parties and certain conservative NGOs focusing on family values proclaimed that the

Convention brings the introduction of a 'third gender' and the massive dominance of the 'gender ideology.' These were presented as to foreign interests which are trying to corrupt Bulgarian society and, most importantly, to expose Bulgarian children to debauchery and immorality.

The conservative voices are thought to be linked to Russian propaganda and paid internet 'troll factories' that were blasting impressive amounts of online content against the Convention. That is how, eventually - after months of media and online anti-Convention campaigns, the term 'gender' in the Bulgarian language came to be a derogatory term - a deviant or another person with unusual and immoral sexual preferences and behaviour. Today 'gender' is a common offence among teenagers and adults alike, instead of the usual rude versions of 'homosexual'.

In this sense, the massive push against the Istanbul Convention brought impressive results for the conservative agenda in Bulgaria. This discussion about the 'third gender' essentially blocked fully any meaningful debate about gender-based violence, violence against women, and similar crucial topics. For a country like Bulgaria, where GBV had been a virtually unrecognised issue, this was detrimental. Any mention of the word 'gender', as in 'gender-based violence,' immediately brings a negative predisposition in a large number of people, including politicians and civil servants in the state institutions. At the time of writing this report, there does not seem to be any political and social will to overcome the 'gender' crisis.

Due to all of these events and factors, the attempt for ratification of the Istanbul Convention did not have any tangible effect specifically on the treatment of the GBV topic in universities and research organisations. There was no specific debate about the application of the Convention in universities and research organisations. The only related action was that a group of 286 scientists, professors and researchers signed a petition in favour of the ratification of the Convention. Apparently, this did not influence the ratification process.

4. PUBLIC OPINION ON GBV

The current research could not identify any relevant national public opinion surveys about GBV at all. For this reason, it is not possible to make an assessment of public opinion based on research results.

The rare attempts of researchers to conduct surveys among students in universities regarding sexual violence and GBV have not been met with understanding or enthusiasm by the staff or by students. For example, Prof. Miglena Todorova initiated such a project in 2016 in a couple of Bulgarian universities, aiming to research sexual violence. However, her research was met with resistance from deans and professors, and very few students actually took part in the survey.

As a whole, GBV does not seem to be perceived as a separate issue or an issue of importance in Bulgarian society. As noted earlier, it is often confused with domestic violence or mentioned alongside it. Crimes based on discrimination of any kind,

including gender, are not treated as a separate category either. Thus, it is safe to conclude that there is no clear public opinion on GBV, as the issue is not understood well.

Some common reactions to the GBV topic are that it may be a made-up issue, that it's a part of a 'gender ideology' coming from the West, and similar. These opinions can be linked to conservative and pro-Russian propaganda.

5. IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON DISCUSSIONS ABOUT GBV

As there is no available information on discussions about GBV in universities and research organisations, it is difficult to assess if the COVID-19 pandemic had an impact on such discussions. Most likely, there have not been any discussions about GBV in the context of academia, and it does not appear that COVID-19 has changed that.

In the public discourse, the issue of domestic violence against women rose to prominence in relation to the COVID-19 lockdowns, as the cases grew significantly in the last year.

6. CONCLUSION

Bulgaria seems to be one of the countries in the EU that has a long way ahead to recognising and dealing with gender-based violence as a whole, and in particular in the context of universities and research organisations.

Before any specific policies can be created, it would be essential to promote a better understanding of GBV amongst the political circles, as well as within the civil servants in different state institutions. It is also important to boost the general understanding of the issue within society as a whole because there is clear resistance towards issues related to 'gender'. A small number of NGOs have been trying to do that for years now, but their resources are limited.

Due to the specificities of the situation in Bulgaria, it would be worth exploring whether more international funding could be directed straight to reputable NGOs with a proven track record that could prepare and apply awareness-raising campaigns and other activities. The NGO and civil society sector are the most active in relation to gender equality and GBV topics, so a change can be spurred by stimulating their potential for action, rather than relying on the state actions, which are often slow and uncoordinated and may lack understanding of the issues at hand.

Some such organisations include the Bulgarian Centre of Women in Technology (part of the European Centre for Women in Technology), Center of Women's Studies and Policies, Bulgarian Gender Research Foundation, Gender Project in Bulgaria, Foundation Gender Alternatives, Bulgarian Fund for Women, and Alliance for Protection against Gender-Based Violence, among others.

What has worked until now with countries like Bulgaria that are lagging behind in terms of gender equality and GBV laws and policies (and their practical power to change the status quo) is to introduce more European-level policies that are obligatory for all member states. It is a top-down method that sometimes evokes resistance, but it has worked in a number of policy areas.

A combination of grassroots and NGO activities and a top-down push from European policies may thus help Bulgaria make a step forward in treating GBV in all the different social contexts, including that of higher education and research organisations.

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